

CH₃), 1.30 (6H, br, s, CH₂), 1.99 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable OH) and 3.61 (2H, t, J₁, J₂ 6 Hz, CH₂OH). The two singlets at δ 0.91 and 0.93 (3H each) are due to the *gem*-dimethyl protons which are also apparent from the characteristic ir bands at 1385 and 1360 cm⁻¹. The singlet at δ 1.99 (1H exchangeable with D₂O) and a triplet at δ 3.61 (2H, J₁, J₂ 6 Hz) suggest the primary nature of the hydroxyl group². The broad singlet at δ 1.30 suggest the presence of long carbon chain in Mm₁ (integrating for 61 protons). The ¹³C nmr spectra (80 MHz, noise-decoupled and SFORD spectra) of Mm₁ provided an unambiguous proof of the structure. The signals confirmed the presence of a *gem*-dimethyl group and a primary alcoholic group in the compound Mm₁. The signals were obtained at δ (CDCl₃) 62.85 (t, C-1), 32.66 (t, C-2), 25.55 (t, C-3), 30.47 (t, C-4), 31.70 (t, C-31), 25.04 (d, C-32), 22.44 (q, C-33, C-33') and 29.22–29.64 (t, other CH₂ carbons). The downfield signal at 62.85 ppm(t) was assigned for the carbon bearing the hydroxyl group⁴. The *gem*-dimethyl carbons, at C-33 and C-33' appeared at 22.44 ppm(q) and the C-32 signal appeared at 25.04 ppm(d). The mass-fragmentation pattern was in conformity with the structure, (CH₃)₂CH.(CH₂)₃₀CH₂OH, the significant ion-peaks appearing at *m/z* 494 (M⁺, 0.70), 476 (0.74), 462 (0.42), 451 (4.20), 448 (2.20), 406 (1.74), 392 (2.76), 97 (62.41), 83 (62.60), 57 (100) and 43 (92.65). The loss of 18 mu (*m/z* 476) and 43 mu (*m/z* 451) from molecular ion peak postulated the presence of the hydroxyl group at one end and the *gem*-dimethyl group at the other⁵.

The leaves also afforded ursolic acid⁶, C₃₀H₄₈O₈ (M⁺ 456), and the structure was confirmed by m.p., m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra with an authentic sample. The extract also yielded another triterpenoid, C₃₂H₄₈O₄ (M⁺ 496), m.p. 314–17°d, [α]_D²⁵ +39 (chloroform) but no further work was possible on this compound due to paucity of the material.

The de-fatted ethyl acetate extract of the flower of this plant afforded *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, gallic acid and kaempferol⁷.

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Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper using Mixed Ligand Complex Formation with Pyridine, α -Picoline, β -Picoline, γ -Picoline or 2,4,6-Collidine and Bromide/Iodide

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REFERENCE to pyridine as an auxiliary ligand in the solvent extraction of metals is not new in the literature. Use of pyridine–thiocyanate for extractive-photometric determination of various metals is well known¹⁻⁶. It has been noted that copper(II) forms complexes with pyridine bases in presence of potassium bromide or potassium iodide. The mixed ligand complexes are extractable into chloroform. These properties of the copper complexes suggested that further studies of the systems might lead to the development of a simple spectrophotometric method for the determination of copper. Apart from pyridine, some of its methyl-substituted derivatives used are α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine.

Experimental

Spectral curves and analytical measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer. Stopped quartz cells of 10 mm optical path length were used for absorbance measurements.

A stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving CuSO₄.5H₂O in distilled water followed by its standardisation as benzoin- α -oximate⁷. A working solution of Cu^{II} (120 μ g ml⁻¹) was prepared by dilution. Chloroform (E. Merck), pyridine (B.D.H.), α -picoline (Riedel), β -picoline (B.D.H.), γ -picoline (Fluka) and 2,4,6-collidine (B.D.H.) were

NOTES

TABLE 1—PARAMETERS OF EXTRACTIVE METHODS

Parameter	Base employed				
	Pyridine	α -Picoline	β -Picoline	γ -Picoline	2,4,6-Collidine
	Bromide system				
pH	1.5–2.5	1.5–2.5	1.5–2.5	1.5–2.5	1.5–2.5
$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	340	320	340	340	355
Molar absorptivity ($\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	2.17	3.07	3.23	2.33	5.13
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.029	0.021	0.018	0.027	0.012
	Iodide system				
pH	0.5–1.5	0.5–1.5	0.5–1.5	0.5–1.5	0.5–1.5
$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	355	*	350	360	360
Molar absorptivity ($\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	2.38	2.65	4.23	4.76	6.77
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.027	0.024	0.015	0.013	0.009

*Absorbance measured at 350 nm.

distilled before use. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of desired diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts. Potassium chloride–hydrochloric acid buffer was used to adjust pH of the aqueous solution.

General procedure :

Bromide system : An aliquot containing 50–300 μg of copper was mixed with 8 *M* aqueous potassium bromide (1 ml) followed by the addition of 0.5 ml of pyridine/ α -picoline, β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine. Buffer solution (5 ml) of pH 2.0 was then added to it and the volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The mixture was then equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 1 min. The separated organic layer was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove any retained water droplets. Finally the absorbance of the organic extract was measured at corresponding absorption maxima against chloroform. The amount of copper(II) was determined from a calibration curve. To test the effect of foreign ions, the respective ions were added to the system before addition of the reagents.

Iodide system : An aqueous solution containing 50–300 μg Cu was mixed with 0.05 *M* potassium iodide (3 ml) and 0.5 ml of pyridine/ α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine. Buffer solution (5 ml) of pH 1.0 was then added followed by distilled water to make the volume of the aqueous phase upto 10 ml. The other part of the procedure was the same as for the bromide system.

Results and Discussion

In presence of pyridine and alkali thiocyanate, copper forms an insoluble complex⁷ of formula $\text{CuPy}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, where thiocyanate behaves as a pseudo-halogen. In presence of bromide/iodide and pyridine bases copper(II) probably forms complexes of the type CuP_2X_2 (P=pyridine base; X=Br/I). These complexes are extractable into chloroform.

The effect of pH on the extractibility of copper(II) into chloroform was examined in terms of absorbance of the mixed ligand complex. The optimum pH of extraction for bromide system was 1.5–2.5 and for iodide system, 0.5–1.5. In both the cases, after a second consecutive operation, the chloroform extract showed virtually no absorbance. This indicated a complete and quantitative extraction of copper in these conditions.

The spectra were scanned in the region 300–600 nm against chloroform. The copper(II)-bromide-pyridine/ α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine complexes in chloroform showed absorption maxima at 320–355 nm (Table 1) with a shoulder at around 380 nm in each case.

In the copper(II)-iodide-pyridine/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine systems, the absorption maxima were at 350–360 nm (Table 1). The copper(II)-iodide- α -picoline complex exhibited no absorption maxima in the region 300–600 nm; in this case the analytical measurements were carried out at 350 nm. The reagent blanks did not absorb in the aforesaid wavelength region. Hence for simplicity all the absorbance measurements were carried out at respective absorption maxima against chloroform.

The systems conformed to Beer's law over a concentration range of 5–50 ppm of copper. The corresponding molar absorptivities of the complexes (on the basis of copper content) and Sandell's sensitivities were calculated (Table 1).

For bromide complexes, 1 ml of 8 *M* aqueous solution of potassium bromide along with 0.5 ml of pyridine bases was sufficient to extract 240 μg of copper(II) at pH 2.0. For iodide complexes the amounts of reagents required were 3 ml of 0.05 *M* potassium iodide along with 0.5 ml of pyridine bases to extract the same amount of copper; in this case the extraction was carried out at pH 1.0. In all cases the organic extracts produced a steady absorbance for at least 24 h.

In order to study the effects of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour, 240 μg of copper(II) was extracted and determined according to the general procedure in presence of the respective foreign ions. For bromide complexes the system tolerates 10–25-fold excess of the following ions: Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , V^{V} , Rh^{III} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Be^{II} , Tl^{I} , U^{VI} , Zr^{IV} , La^{III} , Al^{III} , Th^{IV} , Mg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mo^{IV} . Pt^{IV} and Hg^{II} are permissible at lower concentrations. Pd^{II} however shows strong interference even at trace level. Among the anions tested, most of them are susceptible to the procedure, although phthalate, borate and phosphate do not interfere. In case of iodo complexes, 10–25-fold excess of the following ions are permissible: Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{IV} , V^{V} , Rh^{III} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Zr^{IV} , U^{VI} , Al^{III} , Be^{II} , La^{III} , Tl^{I} . The system tolerates lower concentration of Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} and Fe^{III} . However, Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV} must be absent. Among the anions tested borate, bromide, phthalate, phosphate do not interfere. The presence of thiosulphate, EDTA, tartrate, oxalate, citrate, fluoride, ascorbate restricts the extraction of copper. High results are obtained in presence of thiocyanate.

Among the bases used 2,4,6-collidine was found to be most sensitive in both the bromide and iodide systems. With this reagent the precision and accuracy of the method was tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of copper(II) following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations indicated the proposed method to be fairly precise and reproducible in either of the systems.

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